

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B408
 Date: 26 October 2008
 Take Off: 10:05:05
 Landing: 15:05:44
 Flight Time 5h 00m 39s

Campaign: VOCALS

Operating Area: South east pacific ocean off west coast of northern Chile

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
6	Mission Scientist 3	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
7	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
8	Core Chem / Buck / FTP	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
10	SWS / SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
11	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
12	MARSS / DEIMOS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
13	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
14	AMS / SP2	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
15	Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
16	VACC	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University	
17	Manchester cloud	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
18	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B408
 Date: 25 October 2008
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: Arica, Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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094232		Buck	0.12 kft	001	started
094246		GIN	0.12 kft	001	started
100032		ASP	0.11 kft	018	open
100505		T/O	0.08 kft	199	Arica
100505	101947	Profile 1	0.56 - 10.0 kft	206	late stop mark
100722		psap	2.7 kft	230	flow off
100739		heimann	3.0 kft	224	open
100753		JW	3.3 kft	221	on
100824		psap	4.0 kft	216	flow on
102158		transit	10.0 kft	229	
102235		nev	10.0 kft	227	zero
102242	103308	Profile 2	10.0 - -.03 kft	227	50ft
102906		jw	3.3 kft	225	zero
102919		cloud	3.2 kft	225	top
103017		cloud	2.3 kft	229	base
103026		qnh	2.1 kft	227	1018
103047		psap	1.8 kft	223	flow on
103309	103359	Profile 3	-.03 - 0.33 kft	222	50ft 500ft
103359	104917	Run 1	0.33 - 0.41 kft	220	500ft
103717		bbr	0.39 kft	221	retract
103840		heimann	0.41 kft	222	cal 10
103915	104917	Run 2.1	0.41 kft	240	Point alpha
104917	110019	Profile 4	0.77 - 3.1 kft	267	
105103		p4	2.1 kft	261	interrupt
105212		nev	2.2 kft	267	zero
105221		JW	2.2 kft	268	zero
105938		cloud	2.8 kft	263	entering
105957		p4	3.1 kft	267	restarted
110019	111256	Run 2.2	3.1 - 3.5 kft	265	
110541		manouvre	3.4 kft	263	to re-enter cloud
111257	111403	Profile 5	3.5 - 4.7 kft	263	
111404	112414	Run 2.3	4.7 kft	263	
112434		!	4.9 kft	271	pop up manouvre
112457	113127	Profile 6	5.2 - 0.09 kft	270	
112610		cloud	4.1 kft	268	top
112717		cloud	3.1 kft	265	base
113138		!	0.16 kft	266	pop up
113150	114229	Run 3.1	0.33 - 0.32 kft	266	
113754		heimann	0.35 kft	265	cal 10
114229	114621	Profile 7	0.32 - 3.9 kft	269	
114520		psap	2.9 kft	263	off
114622	115631	Run 3.2	3.9 - 3.8 kft	260	
114643		!	3.8 kft	266	manouver adjustment
115631	115737	Profile 8	3.8 - 4.7 kft	268	
115738	120742	Run 3.3	4.7 - 4.8 kft	265	
120049		heimann	4.8 kft	265	cal06
120801		!	5.1 kft	268	pop up manouvre
120813	121427	Profile 9	5.3 - 0.03 kft	267	
121352		!	0.29 kft	268	point bravo
121503	122527	Run 4.1	0.32 - 0.35 kft	266	
121841		qnh	0.32 kft	267	1020
122528	122909	Profile 10	0.35 - 4.0 kft	266	
122909	123920	Run 4.2	4.0 kft	078	
123921	124012	Profile 11	4.0 - 4.7 kft	095	
124012	125041	Run 4.3	4.7 kft	089	
125041	130112	Profile 12	4.7 - 14.9 kft	089	
130112	131841	Profile 13	14.9 - -.10 kft	089	
131841	131903	Profile 14	-.10 - 0.34 kft	092	
131904	132932	Run 5.1	0.34 - 0.38 kft	094	
132933	133258	Profile 15	0.39 - 3.8 kft	093	

133258	134406	Run 5.2	3.8 - 3.9 kft	093
134407	134522	Profile 16	3.9 - 4.7 kft	095
134523	135509	Run 5.3	4.7 - 4.8 kft	092
135509	140056	Profile 17	4.8 - 0.06 kft	063
140118	141136	Run 6.1	0.31 - 0.34 kft	094
140438		heimann	0.37 kft	092 cal 10
140533		nev	0.37 kft	092 zero
141136	141501	Profile 18	0.34 - 3.2 kft	094
141501	142530	Run 6.2	3.2 - 3.0 kft	095
142531	142616	Profile 19	3.0 - 3.7 kft	069
142616	143647	Run 6.3	3.7 kft	046
143648	143725	Profile 20	3.6 - 3.3 kft	045
143726	144753	Run 6.4	3.3 kft	043
145420		nev	5.0 kft	050 zero
145512		JW	5.0 kft	047 zero (ok)
145615		heimann	4.9 kft	049 cal08
150544		Land	0.05 kft	016 Arica
150813		ASP	0.09 kft	199 closed

B408 Track 26-OCT-08

SCAR -> SCD A - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-10 Expired: Thursday, 23 October 2008.
Scale: 1:3213915 (1 inch = 44.08 naut mi). Printed on 25 Oct 2008

76996 ; 68
FliteStar 9.4.2.0

VOCALS Flight B408
FAAM sortie brief

Sunday 26 October, 2008

T/O 07:00 local

Operating Area: South East Pacific Ocean, off the west coast of northern Chile, along latitude line 20S

Point Alpha: 72°W 20°S
Point Beta: 77°30'W 20°S

Sortie Objectives: To sample aerosol and Sc cloud as a function of distance from the coast to the pristine background

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud. Near shore marine boundary layer winds from SSW.

Flight patterns:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 10,000 ft to check instrumentation before profile descending to 50' at 1000 ft/min
[25 min; T=0h 25 min]
2. Continue to point **alpha** either in cloud or below cloud at 500 ft
[0 min; T=0h 25 min]
3. Perform cycle of 3 times 10-min straight/level legs in order, 500ft amsl, in-cloud (level chosen by Miss.Sci.), 500ft above cloud top. Legs separated by profile ascent 1000ft/min
[45 min; T=1h 10 min]
4. Repeat item 3.
[45 min; T=1h 55 min]
5. Repeat item 3. Turn to return eastwards on reaching point beta.
[45 min; T=2h 40 min]
6. Profile ascent to FL150, 1000ft/min
[10 min; T=2h 50 min]
7. Profile descent to 50ft amsl 1000ft/min
[20 min; T=3h 10 min]
8. Repeat item 3.
[45min; T=3h 55 min]
9. Repeat item 3 as remaining time allows, to land.
[35min; T=4h 30 min]

Mission Scientist Debrief

26/10/2008

Flight B408

VOCALS

Philip R.A. Brown

Flight 1

Mission profile

Take off from Arica and commence immediate profile ascent 1000ft/min on track towards point Alpha (20S 72W). Followed by profile descent to 50ft and climb back to 500ft amsl. Continued this height to Alpha and then turn onto West heading.

Defined pattern of runs consisting of 10 min straight / level at 500ft, an in-cloud level and 500ft above cloud top. Completed two full cycles heading west followed by 500ft run of 3rd cycle. During climb into cloud, reached maximum westerly point at 79.5W. Completed 3rd cycle of runs on E'ly heading.

From above-cloud level, completed profile ascent 1000ft/min to FL150, followed by immediate profile descent to 50ft.

4th full cycle of 3 level runs completed on E'ly heading followed by 500ft and in-cloud levels of 5th cycle. These latter runs displaced slightly N of 20S to deconflict with other VOCALS aircraft heading Westbound. Above-cloud run of 5th cycle completed whilst heading NE from point Alpha on return to Arica. One final additional in-cloud leg completed prior to commencing Arica approach.

General Comments on cloud conditions

As expected, the cloud base, cloud top and cloud thickness all generally increased with distance west, but only by small amounts. For example:

Position	Cloud base	Cloud top
Climb out from Arica	3200 ft	3600ft
Run cycle 1	2600 ft	4300ft
Run cycle 2	3200ft	4300ft
Run cycle 3 (most westerly)	3100ft	4400ft
Run cycle 4	3200ft	4400ft
Run cycle 5	3000ft	3600ft

Cloud base was generally seen to be variable by $\sim \pm 100$ ft. This variation was clearly associated with spatial structure in humidity on the lower part of the boundary layer with a scale comparable with run length (~ 60 km). This can be associated with the mesoscale circulation systems clearly visible in satellite imagery for this day. Similar mesoscale structure seen in Liquid water content (LWC) during in-cloud legs.

On return to point Alpha, cloud layer was clearly much thinner, maybe only 3-400ft with some broken regions. This is again consistent with imagery features.

From 5000ft during recovery to Arica (above cloud), a distinct step could be seen in cloud top height (delta $\sim 1-200$ ft?) with a change in apparent cloud reflectivity.

Possible signal of descending flow spreading from land over cloud top – part of the diurnal circulation near the coast.

Cloud microphysics

High droplet concentrations were observed throughout, with maybe 250 cm⁻³ close to the coast and 200 cm⁻³ at the westerly point. High sulphate loadings were also observed by the VACC instrument throughout the flight. This indicates possible presence of anthropogenic sulphate throughout. Some drizzle drops were observed throughout with slight increase to the west, but this appears to be low-drizzle conditions throughout the region sampled.

Instrumentation

CVI	good throughout
Wet-Neph	good throughout
SWS/ARIES/MARSS	good throughout but possible problems with MARSS data recording
Core chemistry	CO good throughout NO _x good throughout SO ₂ no signals above threshold Ozone, affected by heat build up before flight
CCN	recording dropout due to PC problem, otherwise OK
VACC	good throughout
Cloud microphysics	all probes appeared OK except CIP-15 (known faulty before takeoff)
LWC	JW and Nevzorov good throughout.
Video cameras	not recorded on this flight

VOCALS

FLIGHT 1

20S X-SEC

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B408** Date 26/10/08 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					T10 ARI, 8/8 Sc, hazy-
		3200			cloud base Decoupled
/		3700			top structure in 13L
102242		10000			Start P2 to 50ft
		5000	↘		elevated NO _x
		3450			cloud top.
		2600			" base 0.4 μm ³
/					high NO _x below cloud
		50ft			end profile.
103359		500ft			Run 1 to pt A.
103915		500ft	266	RW 20S	Start 2.1 pt A.
		"			End 2.1
		2300ft			JW, New zero
					700-500 μm ³ CN
		2600		base variable ±100	no drizzle apparent.
1h 110019		3200			Start 2.2 quite near base
/					LWC out close to zero
110557		3600			climb to remain in cloud.
111000					seeing breaks below.
111300		"			End 2.2 extended for VACC
111404		4800	W		Start 2.3 cloud top 4300
/					cloud top is pretty flat.
					T 15°C Td -30 clearly in the dry layer.
/					200 μm Nd in cloud.
112412		"			End 2.3 & hep up 500ft.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.408** Date 26/10/08 Name Page 2 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
112451		5300 ↘			P6 to 200ft.
		4250			top
		3200			base.
					GE well behaved but over-reading.
/					Basically well mixed BC
113150		500ft			Start 3.1
					UACC high sulphate, still in polluted air.
/					
/					W ~ +/- 0.5 ms ⁻¹
113518					see region of lower cloud base ahead
/					to north of track, will pass below it.
1139					Td rising as pass under the patch.
/					
114226		"			End 3.1 Start P7
/		4000			
		3300			base but patches below
114622		3900			Start 3.2 ^{sw e Neuz} area bit split.
/					Sw peak ~ 0.45
1154					cloud deeper above.
/					low sulphate on UACC
/					200µm OL-1 2DC
		3900			End 3.2 P8
		4360			top
115738		4900			Start 3.3

(1019)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B408** Date Name Page **3** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
120742		4900			End R3.3
120813		5400			Start P9
/		4500			top
		3000			base. maybe bit higher.
/					slight decoupling. 78° 30'
121423		200			End P9
121503		500	W		Start 4.1 ²
/		1020	QNH		High sulphate on VACC.
/			W		End 4.1 start P10
/					profile dints in turn.
1227					see Td variations.
/		3100			base
2.5hr 122909		4200	E		Start 4.2 end P10
/					0.4 gm ⁻³ LWC CVI agree
/					CDP 250 20µm,
					MFSSP 240 14µm.
					low drizzle.
		//			End 4.2
		4400			top
124004		4900	E		Run 4.3 (1 saw 100 deg wind 120 deg when W. bound)
/					
/					scat v. slight penetrations of main top but only
					LWC 0.2 ± 0.1 %
					see salt transition on VACC.
125040		//			End 4.3 Start P12

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.408** Date 26/10/08 Name Page 4 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1258		11500 ↗			low structure in Td during climb.
130112		15000 ↘			Start P3
/					T matching upward profile v. closely
/					Td still cooling down to -39.
/		8500			P ₀ ASP increase at top of stable layer but only to ~30
/		13000			cloud top
		3600			base, but variable as before
/					lower NO _x below cloud than previously.
		500			moisture increase,
131845		500ft	E	76W	End P3 rope finished profile, nearly
131904		500ft			R5.1 half way back to P3A
/					mesoscale structure visible in cloud above.
/					etc 150 Z
/					wind 150 deg, 6 ms ⁻¹
/					cloud still solid above.
3.5hr. 132929		500			End S.1 see Td structure on run scale.
/					ΔTd ~ 2°C
/		3200			in base, lower patch?
133258		4000			Start S-2 end P15
					0.2 gm ⁻³ close to cloud top
					CDP 180, 15µm MFSSP 200 12
/					1-10 L ⁻¹ 2DC 100µm max
/					hwc particles on run scale & smaller, one drops to near zero - entrainment zone.
/					0.3 gm ⁻³ peak.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.408** Date Name Page **5** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134402		4000			End 5.2
		4400			top
134505		4900			Start 5.3 end P
					Td -30 above cloud.
/					PCASP 20 but Ch1 noise.
1353		"			offsetting N of 20S for avoidance of cloud a/c.
135506		4900			End 5.3 start P17
		4150			top.
/		3100			base but some scud below
				19° 48 S	Small open patches in cloud now.
/					with larger open patch E-W to N of track.
140100		200			End P17
140118		500	E		Start 6.1 120 deg / 3-4 ms ⁻¹
141136		"			End 6.1 P18
		3000			base.
		3600			top
141501		3300	E	19 54 S	Start 6.2
141750		3200			cloud layer diagonal thinning.
142126		3100			going thru open patches.
1423		"			cloud thickening again.
					End 6.2
		3400			top
142616		3900	045		Start 6.3 seems solid cloud again. wisps of Ci ahead & above
		"			Td -9°C

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.408** Date Name Page **6** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
143647		-			End 6.3 less O ₃ above cloud than prev.
143726		3400 (1019)			Start 6.4 seems solid cloud.
					CDP 300 14 μm
					MFSSP 250 11 μm
					20C < 10 L ⁻¹ 100 μm max.
					QNH 1016 at ARI.
144726		"			End 6.4
		3800 (1019)			top.
1450		5000			still solid cloud below. 1 or 2 C _u over highest peaks ahead.
1454		"			Passing step in cloud top, spreading out from land. Still 8/8 below but lower albedo?
1456					Transition to brighter cloud ahead and R of track. Haze plumes poss. just above cloud top.
		3900 1016			top.
					Seems like cloud hasn't cleared away from land yet
1505					land.
					No video recorded cos I used the Ethernet cable for w/sci laptop!

Mission Scientist's Log (MS₂) VOCALS

Flight No **B.408** Date **26/10/08** Name **KNBOWER MS₃** Page **1** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
7.00.03	(KNB)				Rolling - Tur
7.04.58	(KNB)				Rolling - RN
7.05.22	(KNB)				T10
7.05.43	KNB			(KNB)	7.00:00 $\equiv$ 10:05.43 (MORAE)
		3200'			Cloud
		3600'			CT.
					VACE saw SO ₄ during profile.
10.29.02		3400			CT.
10.30.10		2500			CB
					Presence of NO _x below cloud
					Lots of SO ₄ - VACE
10.22.42	P2 _s	FL100			
10.33.06	P2 end	500'	222	19°42'/71°42'	1014mb, 0.01Ht, 16.54°/10.48° 6m/s/179°
10.38.09	P3 _s	500'			
10.33.59	P5/R1	500'	221		1000mb, 0.31Ht 15.37°/11.09° 6m/s/179°
10.39.12	R2.1	500' (0.4Ht)	237	19°54'/71°54'	Point A - heading West (New Run No)
					Northern was given ~ 10.20ish
10.49.16	R2.1 and P4 start	500'	268	20°0'/72°34'	Climb to just below CB to do CNV cal.
10.51.04	P4 end	2000'	261	20°0'/72°42'	Just below cloud 9.76°/8.61° 938mb, 6m/s/159°
					CCN values - incredibly steady CN
					~ 700 - also CCN fractions steady at 1/3

Mission Scientist's Log (MSi 2)

Flight No **B.408** Date **26/10/06** Name **K N Bower** Page **2** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					<p>Getth about us - climbed to 3600 ft</p> <p>as while CB/CT is lifting to W.</p> <p>2DC - seeing drizzle drops -</p> <p>2PS - above seeing large particles</p>
				[MOVE DOWN]	
11.12.15					VACE reporting SO ₄ v 1/2 previous
10.56.48					<p>Gentle climb to break cloud to clear</p> <p>to get signal in CV</p>
10.59.29	Ascent	2400 (2.7kft)	263	20°0'/73°15'	Entering CB. 917mb 7.66°/6.7° 6m/s/164°
10.00.01	R2.2.st	3200 (3.0kft)	267	20°0'/73°15'	Start of run in cloud. 50kft 6.36°/7.96, 90kmb
11.09.55	R2.2	3600 (3.5kft)	266	20°0'/74°04'	<p>(climbed to remain in cloud - cloud layer</p> <p>slowing up above from cloud 5.5°/7.31° 6/135° 89kmb</p>
11.12.55	R2.2.e/ps	3500ft	214	20°0'/74°12'	<p>Climbing to go through CT - to 500 above</p> <p>5.78°/7.56°C 890mb 6m/s/135°</p>
11.13.43	PS	4400 (4.3kft)	264		CT (865mb 11.36°/2.47° 5m/s/192°)
11.14.04	PSe/R2.3	4700 (4.6kft)	263	20°0'/74°18'	<p>500 above CT (15.6°/-14.62° 4m/s/202°, 852mb)</p> <p>(?)</p>
					<p>SO₄ - 2800 Still in polluted air</p> <p>- negative is sulphate (much higher than</p> <p>Can get to 29°W</p>
				[MOVE DOWN]	
	P6↓				
11.27.25	P6	3.0kft	265	20°0'/75°2'	CB was ~3200M here; 907mb 6.56°/7.16° 8/152°
11.31.27	P6e/q	500ft (0.0kft)	267	20°0'/75°30'	climbing to 500ft 1009mb 15.5°/8.9° 8m/s/155°
11.31.46	R3.1 st	500ft (0.3kft)	266	20°0'/75°30'	1002mb 14.87°/8.65°C 7m/s/158°, 0.3kft
11.41.10	R3.1				VACE ~ 2000 here
11.42.27	R3.1e/ps	500ft (0.3kft)	269	20°0'/76°18'	1001mb 0.3kft 15.37°/9.75°C 7m/s/158°

Mission Scientist's Log (MSa 2)

Flight No **B.408** Date **26/10/08** Name **K.N. BOWER** Page **3** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11.45.36	P7	3400 (3.2M)	262	20°0'/76°30'	CB 3.2kft 901mb 6.79°/7.19°C 11m/s/170° VACC 900 in cloud
11.46.13	P7 and R3.2st	4000 (3.8M)	259	20°0'/76°30'	cloud run - but too near CT - dropping 851mb
11.44.10					VACC 2000 SO₂ 100H to 3900H to stay in cloud.
11.56.34	R3.2 and P8 st	3900 (3.5M)	268	20°0'/77°12'	Climbing to 500' above CT 850mb 5.57°/8.33° CT at ~ 4400 ft 8m/s/152° VACC ~ 200 only in cloud.
11.57.40	P8 e/ R3.3	500ft + CT. 4800 (4.7M)	265	20°0'/77°18'	850mb 4.97°/-23.36°C 8m/s/144° Quite a bit ^{low} not distinct formation VACC stayed ~ 700 SO ₂ trans (at 500) maintained at 700° lots of miscelany - VACC - quite a bit more at this distance at
12.05.46		4.7M	266	20°0'/77°54'	Climbing 500ft - pilot? 851mb (15.01°/-25.33°) 8m/s/134°
12.07.34	R3.3 End/ ascent	4.7M	268	20°0'/76°0'	end of run at 500 ft up - climbing another 500ft.
12.08.14	end climb P9 start.	5.2M	267	20°0'/76°6'	Start P9 (at 500ft up) 834mb (14.74°/-27.19°) 7m/s/139° end 2 nd SO ₂ - ~ 700° background levels of more thermally stable higher so less SO ₂
12.10.52	P9	3000M	269	20°0'/76°18'	CB - out of cloud (2.8kft) 912mb (7.72°/8.85°) 10m/s/140°
12.13.40	P9 (at B)	0.4M	268	19°54'/76°30'	"Borvo" 995mb 15.09°/10.46° 9m/s/146° continuing.
12.14.27	P9 e/	50H (0.0M)	264	19°54'/76°30'	climbing to 500H from 50ft 1012mb
12.15.02	R4.1 start	500ft (0.2M)	266	19°54'/76°30'	Below cloud run (see VACC report below *) Point Charlie defined 79°30' - new summit peak

79.30 Charlie

* 2400 sharp transⁿ 812 400
- bit more SO₂ next than before

Mission Scientist's Log (MSi 2)

Flight No **B.408** Date **26/10/08** Name **K.N. BOWEN** Page **4** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					AMS now back online at top MCP voltage
					- seeing SO ₄
					2700 on PAst - nearly done - extend run to complete
12.25.26	R4.1g / P10	500 (0.3kPa)	267°	19°54'/71°12'	1000mb 15.2°C/9.52°C 9m/s/149°
					just last 90Sec all ones coming down from 2700 → 1500
					PCASP dropping too
12.26.04	P10	3.1kH	319	20°0'/71°24'	enters cloud 901mb 7.05°C/7.96° 6m/s/145°
12.29.07	R4.2g / P10 end	(4.0kPa)	73°	19°54'/71°24'	4200' w 87kmb 5.41°C/8.36° 6m/s/130°
					350 dropped to background 100. VACC
					0.4 g/m ³ JW - agrees with CVI hygrometer.
					NO ₂ - 1/2 pb low
					CO - 7 ranges ° d longer handle
					O ₃ - }
					UDP - 250 (rise slightly)
					FSSP - 240 (14µm) *
12.39.10	P11 start / R4.2 end	(3.9kPa)	95°	19°54'/76°48'	875mb 4.84°/7.63°C 8m/s/154°
12:40.07	R4.3 start / (P11 end)	400' (4.6kPa)	90°	19°54'/76°42'	852mb 4.45°/-20.19°C 9m/s/116°

* (AMS: SO₄ a by km then below cloud VACC: 250
500 → 150 higher BK (above SO₄))

Mission Scientist's Log (MSci 2)

Flight No **B.408** Date **26/10/08** Name **K.N. BOWER** Page **5** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					CEN smole 1/6 from 20/400 1/20
					0.2% 0.1% (resorting 0.2% fraction)
					VACE - thermally stable shell → sea cult
					transhin - - dist & bigger sizes too
					100-250 nm.
12.50.39	R4.300 / P12s	4.7M	89°	20°0'/76°0'	climbing to 15,000', 89mb 14.96/-25.77 8/117
					VACE 700 nm
					marked drop in CO - 75 → ?
					CO rising (light away from GPU.)
13.01.12	P12/P13	14.9M	89	20°0'/77.3'	Very dry
13.03.10	P13 ↓	13.3M	90	20°0'/77.6'	611mb 4.46°/-39.55°C 6m/s/339°
					Chem CO, O ₃ - wet layer of elevation
					at 10000 ft - now got one coming d
					at 8000 ft
13.12.11	P13	4100 +	90	20°0'/76°30'	CT 871mb 6.23°/-21.92° 7m/s/131°
13.13.22	P13	3000 +	90	20°0'/76°24'	CB 907mb 7.15°/7.46° 8m/s/127
					Core Chem NO ₂ peak was around 7
					Below cloud is now near 4. ??
					CEN larger droplets in 0.2% 120/400
					difference with 0.2 - 0.4% largest yet

Mission Scientist's Log (MSu 2)

Flight No **B.408** Date **26/10/08** Name **K.N BOWER** Page **6** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13.18.32	P13c/P14	50ft	92	20°0/76°6'	1016ft (0.0kft) 16.47°/9.3° 6m/s/104°
13.19.04	P14c/RS1	500ft	94	20°0/76°0'	0.3kft 1000mb 15.25°/8.6i 6m/s/108°
					2000 BK ~ 300 2 nd 1° Trans 120°C too - look up. (VACC).
13.29.32	RS.1c/P15c	500ft			
13.32.19	P15	3.1kft	89	20°0/75°18'	VAcc but less 1600, 903mb 7.35°/8.05° 8m/s/140.
13.32.54	P15c/RS2	4000ft	92	20°0/75°12'	h. cloud min. 3.7kft/882mb 5.69°/7.04° 7m/s/142°
					CDP 118 ϕ 15 FSSD 200 ϕ 12 2DC 1-10 m ³ ~ 200µm CAS 500 /cm ³ 14µm 2DS small stuff, mainly. 200 (Blini 100) - measurable amount - not much
13.04.06	RS.2/P16	4000'	95	20°0/74°30'	end d. includ min 3.8kft 5.42°/8.3° 6m/s/123 879mb
13:45.07	P16c/RS3	4900'	93	20°0/74°24'	4.7kft/852mb 15.11°/19.72°C 5m/s/136°
					350 (BK 200) VACC CCN 200 30.2/20 AMS ... CAS aerosol below cloud 20-30 >600µm + slight coarse mode. PCASP 20 - but maybe chl noise
13:50:50	RS.3	(4.7kft)	86	20°0/74°6'	altered. offsetting for D0228
13.55.05	RS3c/P17	4900	63	19°54'/75°45'	descent to 200ft (4.7kft) 850mb 16.22°/32.3° 3m/s/305°
13.56.09	P17	4100	79	19°54'/75°42'	CT (3.9kft) 876mb 9.27°/16.34° 2m/s/91°

579
622
623
624

Mission Scientist's Log (MS2)

Flight No **B.408** Date **26/10/08** Name **K.N. BOWER** Page **7** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13.56.54	P17	3400			CB (3.2kft) 900mb 6.77°/16.92° 4m/s/129° Can see a few breaks in dead layer now.
14.00.53	P17c / (CMB)	200ft	93	19°48'/73°30'	(0.0kft) 1010mb 15.71°/9.93° 3m/s/134.
14.01.13	R6.1st	500ft	94	19°48'/75°24'	(0.2kft) 1005mb 15.32°/9.91° 4m/s/116. Sharp transition 2500 - BK 400 prevously BK was Magnitude of this is 50% in show tracks
14.11.33	R6.1c / P18	500ft	94	19°48'/72°48'	Clearing to 3600' (0.3kft) 1001mb 15.1°/10.43° 4m/s/155° 3000/600 VACC CEN VACC CN ↑ durs transit CEN ↑ " "
					~ Uniform increase
14.14.39	P18end	3600 (3.4kft)	92	19°54'/72°36'	CT. - dropping down (3.4kft/892mb 2m/s/145° 9.76°/3.9°)
14.14.56	R6.2s	3300 (3.2kft)	95	" "	In cloud run. - bright sunshine! VACC 1800/200
14.17.44	R6.2	3.1kft	108	19°54'/72°24'	Dropping to 3200 - see CB too
14.25.27	R6.2end / P18s	2.0kft	79	20°00'/72°0'	around 'Alpha' 908mb 7.1°/9.14° 3m/s/129° 900m ³ BK 150 VACC
14.26.14	P18c / R6.3st	3900 (3.7kft)	46	19°54'/71°54'	Above CT run 3.7kft/889mb 15.97°/-8.8° 2m/s/31° 900 BK 150 CRC - very stable - 400 cm ³
14.36.45	R6.3c / P20st	3900	46	19°30'/71°24'	3.6kft/885mb 885mb 17.05°/-9.08° 2m/s/107° Core Area 25% less O ₃ now.
14.37.22	P20c / R6.4	3400			In dead - last run 898mb/3.2kft 8.14°/9.28° 3m/s/153°

1100 h200 VACC

50ft end P2, start P3

500ft

Point A, start of 20degS Run out to West

End R2.1 at 500ft, profile P4 start up to just below CB for CVI

End P4, 2000ft just below cloud

Gentle climb to base of cloud to clip to get signal in CVI

Entering Cloud on ascent

Climbed to 3200ft – start R2.2

Having climbed to remain in cloud – now quite thick – odd minor hole – locally – not continuous vertically R2.2 still

End 2.2 – start profile climb P5 to 500 above CT

CT at 4400ft

End P5 start R2.3 at 500ft above CT

CB ~3200ft during P6 descent

50ft end P6 climbing to 500ft

Start R3.1 at 500ft

End R3.1 – profile climb to in-cloud leg P7

P7 CB hit

End P7 start R3.2

End 3.2 P8 start CT at 4400ft

End P8 start R3.3 at 500 above CT

Plot - Internet Explorer provided by Dell

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

Flight B408 12:05:46
Heading 288 deg Speed 228 knots Height 4.7kft Press 851mb
Lat 20°0.0'S Long 77°54.0'W Wind 8 ms-1/ 139 deg
Temp 15.01C Dewpoint -25.37C

Track Plot Plot From: start To: now All

Save plot parameters as Track Plot

Long 663.GIN LONGITUDE (deg (+ve E))

- 659.TECO NOx (ppb)
- 660.NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER (g m-3)
- 661.NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER (g m-3)
- 662.GIN LATITUDE (deg (+ve N))

Lat 662.GIN LATITUDE (deg (+ve N)) Red Line Del

Internet | Protected Mode: On 100%

End Run R3.3 climbing another 500ft

Starting P9 at 500ft up

Out of cloud now

Original point B – continuing on

End P9 at 50ft

Start R4.1 at 500ft VACC reporting lot more here 2400 sharp transition
Lot more SO4 than before

End 4.1 start P10

Entering cloud on p10

End P10, start R4.2

End R4.2 start P11

End P11 start R4.3 at 4900ft C

End R4.3 start P12 to 15000ft

Needed to reinitialise Horace – screens froze up

Profile 10	12:25:28	266	0.35kft	20.0S	79.3W	12:29:09	078	4.0kft	20.0S	79.4W
Run 4.2	12:29:09	078	4.0kft	20.0S	79.4W	12:39:20	095	4.0kft	20.0S	78.8W
Profile 11	12:39:21	095	4.0kft	20.0S	78.8W	12:40:12	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.7W
Run 4.3	12:40:12	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.7W	12:50:41	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.1W
Profile 12	12:50:41	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.1W	13:01:12	089	14.9kft	20.0S	77.3W
Profile 13	13:01:12	089	14.9kft	20.0S	77.3W	13:18:41	092	-.10kft	20.0S	76.1W
Profile 14	13:18:41	092	-.10kft	20.0S	76.1W	13:19:03	094	0.34kft	20.0S	76.1W
Run 5.1	13:19:04	094	0.34kft	20.0S	76.1W	13:29:32	092	0.38kft	20.0S	75.5W
Profile 15	13:29:33	093	0.39kft	20.0S	75.5W	13:32:58	093	3.8kft	20.0S	75.3W
Run 5.2	13:32:58	093	3.8kft	20.0S	75.3W	13:44:06	095	3.9kft	20.0S	74.6W
Profile 16	13:44:07	095	3.9kft	20.0S	74.6W	13:45:22	092	4.7kft	20.0S	74.5W
Run 5.3	13:45:23	092	4.7kft	20.0S	74.5W	13:55:09	063	4.8kft	19.9S	73.9W
Profile 17	13:55:09	063	4.8kft	19.9S	73.9W	14:00:56	093	0.06kft	19.9S	73.5W
Run 6.1	14:01:18	094	0.31kft	19.9S	73.5W	14:11:36	094	0.34kft	19.9S	72.9W
heimann	14:04:38	092	0.37kft	19.9S	73.3W					cal 10
nev	14:05:33	092	0.37kft	19.9S	73.2W					zero
Profile 18	14:11:36	094	0.34kft	19.9S	72.9W	14:15:01	095	3.2kft	19.9S	72.7W
Run 6.2	14:15:01	095	3.2kft	19.9S	72.7W	14:25:30	069	3.0kft	20.0S	72.0W
Profile 19	14:25:31	069	3.0kft	20.0S	72.0W	14:26:16	046	3.7kft	20.0S	72.0W
Run 6.3	14:26:16	046	3.7kft	20.0S	72.0W	14:36:47	046	3.7kft	19.5S	71.5W
Profile 20	14:36:48	045	3.6kft	19.5S	71.5W	14:37:25	043	3.3kft	19.5S	71.5W
Run 6.4	14:37:26	043	3.3kft	19.5S	71.5W					

P13 descent

Plot - Mozilla Firefox

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

Flight B408 13:12:11
 Heading 90 deg Speed 233 knots Height 4.1kft Press 871mb
 Lat 20°0.0'S Long 76°30.0'W Wind 7 ms-1/ 131 deg
 Temp 6.23C Dewpoint -21.92C

Alt [v] Plot From: start To: now All [v]

Save plot parameters as Alt [v]

X 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs) [v]

577.PITOT STATIC PRESSURE (mb) [v]

578.PRESSURE HEIGHT (m) [v]

579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (kft) [v]

580.SOLAR ALBEDO (-) [v]

581.NEAR INFRA-RED ALBEDO (-) [v]

Y1 520.DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (K) Black [v] Line [v] Del

Y2 579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (kft) Red [v] Line [v] Del

Y3

Y4

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

zotero

CT

Plot - Mozilla Firefox

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

Flight B408 13:13:22
 Heading 90 deg Speed 219 knots Height 3.0kft Press 907mb
 Lat 20°0.0'S Long 76°24.0'W Wind 8 ms-1/ 127 deg
 Temp 7.15C Dewpoint 7.46C

Alt [v] Plot From: start To: now All [v]

Save plot parameters as Alt [v]

X 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs) [v]

577.PITOT STATIC PRESSURE (mb) [v]

578.PRESSURE HEIGHT (m) [v]

579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (kft) [v]

580.SOLAR ALBEDO (-) [v]

581.NEAR INFRA-RED ALBEDO (-) [v]

Y1 520.DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (K) Black [v] Line [v] Del

Y2 579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (kft) Red [v] Line [v] Del

Y3

Y4

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

zotero

CB

End P13 at 50

Run 5.1 start end P14

Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

New plot, same times

Flight B408 13:23:53
 Heading 95 deg Speed 201 knots Height 0.3kft Press 1001mb
 Lat 20°0.0'S Long 75°48.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 150 deg
 Temp 15.06C Dewpoint 8.51C
 From start to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 48231 secs
 — PRESSURE HEIGHT 0.32 Kft

All Sci

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

zotero

End R5.1 start P15

P15 into CB

Includ R5.2

Mozilla Firefox
 File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help
 http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

New plot, same times

Flight B408 13:40:37
 Heading 91 deg Speed 219 knots Height 3.8kft Press 880mb
 Lat 20°0.0'S Long 74°42.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 114 deg
 Temp 5.52C Dewpoint 8.39C
 From start to now

408 13:40:37
 91 deg Speed 219 knots Height 3.8kft Press 880mb
 0.0'S Long 74°42.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 114 deg
 5.52C Dewpoint 8.39C

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 49236 secs
 DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 5.53 deg C
 DEW POINT 8.39 deg C

All sci

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

Mozilla Firefox
 File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help
 http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

New plot, same times

Flight B408 13:42:47
 Heading 91 deg Speed 214 knots Height 3.8kft Press 879mb
 Lat 20°0.0'S Long 74°36.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 119 deg
 Temp 5.48C Dewpoint 8.17C
 From start to now

408 13:42:47
 91 deg Speed 214 knots Height 3.8kft Press 879mb
 0.0'S Long 74°36.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 119 deg
 5.48C Dewpoint 8.17C

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 49365 secs
 OZONE MIXING RATIO 24.92 ppb

All sci

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

End R5.2 P16 start

Mozilla Firefox
 File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

Flight B408 13:45:07
 Heading 93 deg Speed 217 knots Height 4.7kft Press 852mb
 Lat 20°0.0'S Long 74°24.0'W Wind 5 ms-1/ 136 deg
 Temp 15.11C Dewpoint -19.72C
 From start to now

Current values
 GIN LONGITUDE -74.5 deg (+ve E) Draw plan
 GIN LATITUDE -20.03 deg (+ve N)

Done

End P16 start R5.3

Offsetting to avoid DO228

End R5.3 start P17 down to 200 ft

CT

P17 CB

P17 end 200ft P18 start

R6.1 start, P18 end

Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

Flight B408 14:08:24
 Heading 90 deg Speed 209 knots Height 0.4kft Press 998mb
 Lat 19°48.0'S Long 73°0.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 137 deg
 Temp 14.81C Dewpoint 9.29C
 From start to now

Current values			
++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	0.41	Kft
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	11.54	m-1
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	11.26	m-1
++++	NEPH RED SP	8.93	m-1

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

New plot, same times

Flight B408 14:08:40
 Heading 90 deg Speed 208 knots Height 0.4kft Press 998mb
 Lat 19°48.0'S Long 73°0.0'W Wind 5 ms-1/ 145 deg
 Temp 14.81C Dewpoint 9.38C
 From start to now

Current values			
---	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	50919	secs
---	NEPH BLUE SP	8.62	m-1
---	NEPH GREEN SP	11.19	m-1
---	NEPH RED SP	10.96	m-1

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

End R6.1 & climbing to 3800ft

P18 end, start R6.2 - not in cloud so descend

R6.2 still not in cloud

Dropping to 3200ft to stay in cloud

R6.2 end, start P19 at 3200ft

End P19, start R6.3 at 3900ft

End R6.3, P20 start

End P20 R6.4 start

Flight Summary B408

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
Buck	09:42:32	001	0.12kft	18.4S	70.3W						started
GIN	09:42:46	001	0.12kft	18.4S	70.3W						started
ASP	10:00:32	018	0.11kft	18.3S	70.3W						open
T/O	10:05:05	199	0.08kft	18.4S	70.3W						Arica
Profile 1	10:05:37	206	0.56kft	18.4S	70.3W	10:19:47	226	10.0kft	19.1S	71.1W	start at t/o late stop mark
psap	10:07:22	230	2.7kft	18.4S	70.4W						flow off
heimann	10:07:39	224	3.0kft	18.5S	70.4W						open
JW	10:07:53	221	3.3kft	18.5S	70.5W						on
psap	10:08:24	216	4.0kft	18.5S	70.5W						flow on
transit	10:21:58	229	10.0kft	19.2S	71.2W						
nev	10:22:35	227	10.0kft	19.2S	71.2W						zero
Profile 2	10:22:42	227	10.0kft	19.2S	71.2W	10:33:08	222	-.03kft	19.7S	71.7W	50ft
jw	10:29:06	225	3.3kft	19.6S	71.5W						zero
cloud	10:29:19	225	3.2kft	19.6S	71.6W						top
cloud	10:30:17	229	2.3kft	19.6S	71.6W						base
qnh	10:30:26	227	2.1kft	19.6S	71.6W						1018
psap	10:30:47	223	1.8kft	19.6S	71.6W						flow on
Profile 3	10:33:09	222	-.03kft	19.7S	71.7W	10:33:59	220	0.33kft	19.8S	71.8W	50ft 500ft
Run 1	10:33:59	220	0.33kft	19.8S	71.8W	10:49:17	268	0.41kft	20.0S	72.6W	500ft
bbr	10:37:17	221	0.39kft	19.9S	71.9W						retract

Run 1	10:33:59	220	0.33kft	19.8S	71.8W	10:49:17	268	0.41kft	20.0S	72.6W	500ft
bbr	10:37:17	221	0.39kft	19.9S	71.9W						retract
heimann	10:38:40	222	0.41kft	20.0S	72.0W						cal 10
!	10:39:15	240	0.41kft	20.0S	72.0W						oint alpha
!	10:41:18	265	0.42kft	20.0S	72.1W						error above this is R2.1 from Alpha
p4	10:49:46	267	0.77kft	20.0S	72.7W						start at end r2.1
p4	10:51:03	261	2.1kft	20.0S	72.8W						interrupt
nev	10:52:12	267	2.2kft	20.0S	72.8W						zero
JW	10:52:21	268	2.2kft	20.0S	72.8W						zero
cloud	10:59:38	263	2.8kft	20.0S	73.3W						entering
p4	10:59:57	267	3.1kft	20.0S	73.4W						restarted
Run 2.2	11:00:19	265	3.1kft	20.0S	73.4W	11:12:56	264	3.5kft	20.0S	74.3W	also end p4
manouvre	11:05:41	263	3.4kft	20.0S	73.7W						to re-enter cloud
Profile 5	11:12:57	263	3.5kft	20.0S	74.3W	11:14:03	263	4.7kft	20.0S	74.3W	
Run 2.3	11:14:04	263	4.7kft	20.0S	74.3W	11:24:14	271	4.7kft	20.0S	75.0W	
!	11:24:34	271	4.9kft	20.0S	75.1W						pop up manouvre
Profile 6	11:24:57	270	5.2kft	20.0S	75.1W	11:31:27	267	0.09kft	20.0S	75.6W	
cloud	11:26:10	268	4.1kft	20.0S	75.2W						top
cloud	11:27:17	265	3.1kft	20.0S	75.3W						base
!	11:31:38	266	0.16kft	20.0S	75.6W						pop up
Run 3.1	11:31:50	266	0.33kft	20.0S	75.6W	11:42:29	269	0.32kft	20.0S	76.3W	
heimann	11:37:54	265	0.35kft	20.0S	76.0W						cal 10
Profile 7	11:42:29	269	0.32kft	20.0S	76.3W	11:46:21	260	3.9kft	20.0S	76.6W	
psap	11:45:20	263	2.9kft	20.0S	76.5W						off

psap	11:45:20	263	2.9kft	20.0S	76.5W													off
Run 3.2	11:46:22	260	3.9kft	20.0S	76.6W	11:56:31	268	3.8kft	20.0S	77.3W								
	11:46:43	266	3.8kft	20.0S	76.6W													manouver adjustment
Profile 8	11:56:31	268	3.8kft	20.0S	77.3W	11:57:37	265	4.7kft	20.0S	77.4W								
Run 3.3	11:57:38	265	4.7kft	20.0S	77.4W	12:07:42	269	4.8kft	20.0S	78.1W								
heimann	12:00:49	265	4.8kft	20.0S	77.6W													cal06
	12:08:01	268	5.1kft	20.0S	78.1W													pop up manouvre
Profile 9	12:08:13	267	5.3kft	20.0S	78.1W	12:14:27	264	0.03kft	20.0S	78.6W								
	12:13:52	268	0.29kft	20.0S	78.5W													point bravo
Run 4.1	12:15:03	266	0.32kft	20.0S	78.6W	12:25:27	266	0.35kft	20.0S	79.3W								
qnh	12:18:41	267	0.32kft	20.0S	78.8W													1020
Profile 10	12:25:28	266	0.35kft	20.0S	79.3W	12:29:09	078	4.0kft	20.0S	79.4W								
Run 4.2	12:29:09	078	4.0kft	20.0S	79.4W	12:39:20	095	4.0kft	20.0S	78.8W								
Profile 11	12:39:21	095	4.0kft	20.0S	78.8W	12:40:12	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.7W								
Run 4.3	12:40:12	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.7W	12:50:41	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.1W								
Profile 12	12:50:41	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.1W	13:01:12	089	14.9kft	20.0S	77.3W								
Profile 13	13:01:12	089	14.9kft	20.0S	77.3W	13:18:41	092	- .10kft	20.0S	76.1W								
Profile 14	13:18:41	092	- .10kft	20.0S	76.1W	13:19:03	094	0.34kft	20.0S	76.1W								
Run 5.1	13:19:04	094	0.34kft	20.0S	76.1W	13:29:32	092	0.38kft	20.0S	75.5W								
Profile 15	13:29:33	093	0.39kft	20.0S	75.5W	13:32:58	093	3.8kft	20.0S	75.3W								
Run 5.2	13:32:58	093	3.8kft	20.0S	75.3W	13:44:06	095	3.9kft	20.0S	74.6W								
Profile 16	13:44:07	095	3.9kft	20.0S	74.6W	13:45:22	092	4.7kft	20.0S	74.5W								
Run 5.3	13:45:23	092	4.7kft	20.0S	74.5W	13:55:09	063	4.8kft	19.9S	73.9W								

Profile 10	12:25:28	266	0.35kft	20.0S	79.3W	12:29:09	078	4.0kft	20.0S	79.4W
Run 4.2	12:29:09	078	4.0kft	20.0S	79.4W	12:39:20	095	4.0kft	20.0S	78.8W
Profile 11	12:39:21	095	4.0kft	20.0S	78.8W	12:40:12	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.7W
Run 4.3	12:40:12	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.7W	12:50:41	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.1W
Profile 12	12:50:41	089	4.7kft	20.0S	78.1W	13:01:12	089	14.9kft	20.0S	77.3W
Profile 13	13:01:12	089	14.9kft	20.0S	77.3W	13:18:41	092	-.10kft	20.0S	76.1W
Profile 14	13:18:41	092	-.10kft	20.0S	76.1W	13:19:03	094	0.34kft	20.0S	76.1W
Run 5.1	13:19:04	094	0.34kft	20.0S	76.1W	13:29:32	092	0.38kft	20.0S	75.5W
Profile 15	13:29:33	093	0.39kft	20.0S	75.5W	13:32:58	093	3.8kft	20.0S	75.3W
Run 5.2	13:32:58	093	3.8kft	20.0S	75.3W	13:44:06	095	3.9kft	20.0S	74.6W
Profile 16	13:44:07	095	3.9kft	20.0S	74.6W	13:45:22	092	4.7kft	20.0S	74.5W
Run 5.3	13:45:23	092	4.7kft	20.0S	74.5W	13:55:09	063	4.8kft	19.9S	73.9W
Profile 17	13:55:09	063	4.8kft	19.9S	73.9W	14:00:56	093	0.06kft	19.9S	73.5W
Run 6.1	14:01:18	094	0.31kft	19.9S	73.5W	14:11:36	094	0.34kft	19.9S	72.9W
heimann	14:04:38	092	0.37kft	19.9S	73.3W					cal 10
nev	14:05:33	092	0.37kft	19.9S	73.2W					zero
Profile 18	14:11:36	094	0.34kft	19.9S	72.9W	14:15:01	095	3.2kft	19.9S	72.7W
Run 6.2	14:15:01	095	3.2kft	19.9S	72.7W	14:25:30	069	3.0kft	20.0S	72.0W
Profile 19	14:25:31	069	3.0kft	20.0S	72.0W	14:26:16	046	3.7kft	20.0S	72.0W
Run 6.3	14:26:16	046	3.7kft	20.0S	72.0W	14:36:47	046	3.7kft	19.5S	71.5W
Profile 20	14:36:48	045	3.6kft	19.5S	71.5W	14:37:25	043	3.3kft	19.5S	71.5W
Run 6.4	14:37:26	043	3.3kft	19.5S	71.5W					

Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html

New plot, same times

Flight B408 14:44:33
 Heading 49 deg Speed 213 knots Height 3.2kft Press 899mb
 Lat 19°12.0'S Long 71°6.0'W Wind 1 ms-1/ 126 deg
 Temp 7.64C Dewpoint 9.94C
 From start to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	53073	secs	☒ All	☒ Sci
—	JAW LIQUID WATER	0.22	g m-3	☐	
—	NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0.12	g m-3	☐	
—	NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	0.14	g m-3	☐	

Applet horaceplot.plot.plotapp started

zotero

End R6.4

Debrief 408

- good W wind penetration
- 5 complete cycles - last alle/ice OK.
- getting high SD_g most of time - VACL

drop comes - 250 clear in } homogeneous
 200 way out west }

scanned fairly well mixed layer - most of deck
 - det meso-scale structure at 500mb level - higher r rrr - lower CB
 - scanned & pick up this.

SD_g - higher further out at times.

15 3 like ralls

17 2 like ralls

possibly get as far as a banders. - Way out west

Equipment -
 - power change over deck list

Inst - Core OK - glitches - MSe 3 layer
 - MSe 1 external connect
 -

CHI ✓
 North / West North ← wind turning at end - lost comm
 SMS - fine with most
 sensors received a bit
 AMS - data coming for return - SMP5 ✓
 Core Chem - CO - working well
 - SO₂ fine - saw nothing
 NO_x fine
 O₃ - OK but heat affected - get bars affected

2DS - fine
 COPS - fine
 Buck - ✓
 Arrows - turned on but external
 cable full out so lost
 comms
 Filler -

Cloud Phys - Hard dist on FSS
 - noise on inst

Arctic - OK
 Mon - not recording data wr b
 R.3.1

CEN - worked really well
 10 min Blue Scan
 (install then only a)
 too hot for CPC @ 130

VACL - pretty damn good
 CPE - diffused noise
 PAV - recorded & little

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B408** Date **26/10/08** Name **P. BARRETT** Page **1** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					M
10.07		3.0			HIGH LWC - SPIKE @ ~ 0.8 g/m ³ - SW HIGH LWC - IN CLOUD
10.18 10.18	P2	10000 → 8000			IN CLOUD T=7.5
10.30	R1	3000	W		sub cloud - head to PORT X
			W		CLOUD BASE ~ 2500
			W		CLOUD TOP ~ 3400
			W		⊕ CLOUD LWC - Never ~ 1.0 g/m ³ Prof to cloud
			W		
10.44.00	P4	5000-2000	W		Profile to sub cloud - CUI zero.
10.50.00	R				CUI, AWS zero, vertical wind sub cloud - peak ~ 1.0 m/s ¹ wind @ 18°
10.58.00	P4				climbs to cloud base - CUI set up! sub cloud depth > T
11.00.19	R2.2	3200			in cloud
11.02					big increase in LWC, JW, Neph can see sea surface on occasions Correlated with big down draft 11.02
					Cloud base rising away from coast, climbs to 3400
11.05	R2.1	3400			thicker cloud, → drizzle cloud physics never seen below JW by ~ 0.1, 0.2 g/m ³

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B/A08** Date **26/12/08** Name **P. BARRETT** Page **2** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11.10					Down draft - increase in LWC EXTEND RUN FOR VACC, sulphate transp.
					Vertical velocity - regular cell structure?
11.15	P2.1 P10				
11	P15				cloud base 4.4 kft
					Profile Down SW is -ve above cloud.
11.27					cloud base 3200 @ 75° 18' cloud base 4100
11.31.15	23.1				L.c.f. RI, base 2.5, top 3.4 kft major sulphate below cloud, more below than in cloud wind 7ms ¹ 138° SW Moisture increasing (Dewpoint) along the run. generally W is +ve
11.42.29	P7				cloud base = 3.2 kft. stronger turbulence near cloud base.
11.46	P32	43.9			Cu -11 -14 EF = 40 LWC ~ 0.25 gm ⁻³ 0.25 → 0.35 gm ⁻³ - due to SW

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B408** Date **26/10/08** Name **P. BARRETT** Page **3** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					wind has a larger westward component at higher altitude
					160° @ 500ft
					130° @ 5000ft
12:06.13	P9				Cloud top @ 4.4 kft cloud base @ 2.8 kft
12:15:03	R4.1	300ft	W		lots of sulphate
12:20					AMS logging again
12:25	P10	4.2 kft			turn in climb - heading W cloud base @ 3.2 kft
	R4.2	4.2	East		in cloud ~ 0.4 g m ⁻³
					CU agrees
					directly above previous 300ft
					big spikes in CO data - cloud?
					Drizzle on wings
12:35					CDP - 250 $\phi = 20 \mu\text{m}$ FSDPM 240 $\phi = 14 \mu\text{m}$
12:38.4	P11	4.2 → 4.9	E		climb above cloud.
					cloud top ~ 4.1 kft - so must be falling, lower cloud top at this point - appears to be around leg.

4.4 ~ 4.4

3.2 ~ 3.2 ← cloud base - OUTBOUND

•ARI

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B408**... Date **26/10/08**... Name **P. BARRETT**... Page **4** of **6**...

B:12

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	P13				Profile very dry aloft
	"				no structure
	"				Dewpoint depression > 40°C
	"				
	ACT	4.1	E	76.3W	Cloud base @ 4.1 kft
	CB	3.4	E	76.24W	cloud base @ 3.4 kft
					No increase on Profile
13:18:41		500			lower than previous
13:18:04	S1	500	E	76.00	
13:	P15	500 → 4.1	E	75.24	Saturation before cloud
13:32:56	S2	4.2 kft	E	75.12	Cloud base @ 3.1 kft
					COP 180 cc ³ @ 15µm
					GSP 200 cc ³ @ 12µm
					2-IX 1 → 10 per litre phs 10µm
					AS 500 cc ³ ?
					ZDS small stuff, few fibres - 5µm?
13:39				76.48	Clc increasing
13:41					cloud thinning? brighter from above
					increased turbulence?
					- cloud top entrainment?
					Dirt on windows
13:44:07	P16	4.1-4.4		74.30°	dimly above cloud
					cloud top = 4.1 kft
13:44:23	R53	4.9	E	74.24°	

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B4.08** Date 26/12/08 Name P. BARRETT Page 5 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1346	R53	A.9			sulphate slightly higher than rd-mech
13:55	P17	42→02			- diversion due to DORNIER
					cloud base @ 3.9 kft
					cloud base - above 2.8 kft -
					probably ~ 31 or 32 kft
					- so, thinner than outboard
					by by a couple of hundred feet
					possibly,
					broken in places visible from
					below,
14.00	R6.1	500ft	96deg	73.24	
					⊕ JW has a high readout after the
					cloud passage w.f. before
					Max spike is lower again
14.06					cloud cover is now more complete
					again in this area
14.11	P18	500			cloud base @ ???
					cloudtop @ 3.5 kft
14.15.01	R6.2	33			IN @ CLOUD
					Some breaks above, bright
14.17		32			drooping as cloudtop falls off
					near cloud base now
14.23		3.1??			cloud base -

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/10/26 18:48

Author of report: PHIL BROWN

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/10/26 18:51

Remaining flight hours: c.60

General Comments:

After first flight on 26/10/2008

INSTRUMENTS / SYSTEMS STATUS

 = no report

Meteorology / Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
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10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:	
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:	
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:	
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:	
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment:	problems with lower instrument
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:	

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:	
17.	NO _x	Comment:	
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:	
19.	SO ₂ (TECO 43C)	Comment:	
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:	
21.	CH ₄ /CO ₂ (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:	
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment:	
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:	
24.	CH ₄ /N ₂ O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:	

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	
42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	

43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Chemistry Log

Date: *B408*

Flight: *26/10/08*

Operator: *KFT*

Preflight *SO₂ on as well as O₃(49c), NO_x + CO.*

No. ? or x	Location	Action	Comments						
Gases									
1	☒ CO2/Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">190</td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">48</td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">50</td></tr> </table>	190	48	50			
190									
48									
50									
2	☒ CO2/Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi							
3	☒ CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar							
4	☒ CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure							
5	☒ Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar							
6	☒ Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure							
Flows									
7	☒ Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 0.7 LPM on both channels	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">1.0</td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> </table>	1.0					
1.0									
8	☒ NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM							
9	☒ NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM							
10	☒ CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min							
11	☒ CO cell pressure	~ 7.5 bar							
12	☒ CO Pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar							
Zeros									
13	☒ Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">-1.0</td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">0.17, 1.31, 1.50</td></tr> </table>	-1.0	0.17, 1.31, 1.50				
-1.0									
0.17, 1.31, 1.50									
14	☒ NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)							
15	☒ CO zero	Left for approx 10 min							
Other									
16	☒ Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;"><i>Manual valve turns to be used.</i></td></tr> </table>			<i>Manual valve turns to be used.</i>			
<i>Manual valve turns to be used.</i>									
17	☒ HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded							
18	☒ CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)							
TDLAS									
19	☒ 230V	230V power breakers on	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> </table>						
20	☒ 28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)							
21	☒ Laptop	On and software working							
22	☒ Data	Being saved to correct directories							
Post Flight									
Switch off									
1	☒ CO	Switch off instrument	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> </table>						
2	☒ Ozone	Switch off monitor							
3	☒ NOx	Switch off monitor							
4	☒ Pumps	Switch off all pumps							
5	☒ Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP							
Gases (note pressures)									
6	☒ CO2/Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">190</td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">50</td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">50</td></tr> </table>	190	50	50			
190									
50									
50									
7	☒ CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi							
8	☒ Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling							
Driers									
9	☒ Small drier	Change if spent	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> </table>						
10	☒ Large drier	Change if spent							
TDLAS									
11	☒ Data transfer	To memory stick	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> </table>						
12	☒ Laptop	Shut down							
13	☒ Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on							
Log									
14	☒ Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 100%;"> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> </table>						
15	☒ Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder							
16	☒ TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC							

Chemistry Log

B408

In flight

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.

During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
10:02	Post power change	88.50	345	30566	40.54	7.53
10:43	500FT	Manual valve turn		~30250	40.53	7.53
10:31	500FT	Manual valve turns		~30600	39.13	7.59
12:16	500FT	Manual valve turns		~30500	38.69	7.53
13:19	500FT	Manual valve turns		~30500	38.60	7.52
14:04	500FT	Manual valve turns			38.47	7.53
14:50	~FL070	Manual valve turns			38.40	7.53

23.57
159198

In flight comments

- NOT informed about power changeover → CO instrument fell over
 - Cabin ✓ LOT before take off - O₃ overheating
 - CO data set to store at 1Hz pre-flight

B408 CO manual calibration

10:35	515 ppb	76000 Hz	-3 ppb	30250 Hz	40.53
11:31	530 ppb	77500 Hz	+1 ppb	30600 Hz	39.13
12:16	535 ppb	78000 Hz	0 ppb	30500 Hz	38.69
13:19	535 ppb	78000 Hz	-1 ppb	30500 Hz	38.60
14:07	530 ppb	77200 Hz	-4 ppb	30400 Hz	38.47
	530 ppb	77300 Hz	-4 ppb	30100 Hz	38.40

B409

20:16	505 ppb	74300 Hz	-5 ppb	29700 Hz	40.52
21:03	510	75200 Hz	-3 ppb	29800 Hz	40.40
21:42	524	76600 Hz	1 ppb	29900 Hz	38.65
22:19	528	77000 Hz	-1 ppb	30000 Hz	37.31
23:23	526	77000 Hz	-2 ppb	29800 Hz	37.61

B411

11:10	495 ppb	79500 Hz	-6 ppb	30000 Hz	35.87
11:39	490 ppb	78900 Hz	-10 ppb	29600 Hz	36.53
12:20	485 ppb	78800 Hz	-12 ppb	29300 Hz	37.33
13:00	485 ppb	78800 Hz	-12 ppb	29200 Hz	37.64
13:59	480 ppb	78200 Hz	-15 ppb	29000 Hz	37.99
15:06	478 ppb	77700 Hz	-15 ppb	29000 Hz	38.26

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 408

Date: 26/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	MVD	LWC		
10:09:30	70	0.08	119													FL050	
10:10:19	65	0.08														FL060	
10:15:13	25	0.07														End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ FL100	
10:16:00	20	0.07															
10:18:00	20	0.08	120														
10:20:00	15	0.08															
10:22:00	15	0.08															
10:22:40	10	0.07														End of Run & Start P2 from FL100	
10:23:50	20	0.07														FL090	
10:24:41	20	0.08														FL080	
10:25:43	60	0.08														FL070	
10:26:38	100	0.08														FL060	
10:27:38	95	0.08														FL050	
10:28:33	95	0.08														FL040	
10:29:35	190	0.17	218					140	10							FL030	
10:30:28	260	0.08	300													FL020	
10:31:24	300	0.08	301													FL010	
10:33:08	250	0.08														End of Profile 2 @ 50'	
10:34:01																Start Run 2.0 @ 500'	
10:35:00	230	0.08															
10:37:00	275	0.08															
10:39:13	260	0.08														Point A (Start Run 2.1)	
10:40:00	200	0.08															
10:42:00	160	0.08	302														
10:44:00	190	0.08															
10:46:00	180	0.08	393														
10:48:00	170	0.08	397														
10:49:19	130	0.08	404													End of Run 2.1 & Start Profile 4	
10:50:03																	
10:51:08																Start Run 2.2 @ FL022	
10:52:00	140	0.08															
10:54:00	150	0.08	406														
10:58:51																End of Run @ Start P4 from FL022	
11:00:00																End of P4 & Start Run 2.2 @ FL031	
11:01:00	100	0.18	1057			10	100	130	9				250	10	0.2	12	
11:03:00	120	0.21	2374			2	100	45	10				200	10	0.2	12	
11:05:00	90	0.08	3228			1		0.5	5				100	10	0.25	12	
11:07:00	370	0.35	4433			10	100	200	10				200	13	0.3	12	
11:09:00	140	0.27	6399			4	150	160	12				200	12	0.2	12	
11:11:00	240	0.34	8296			4	200	210	13				200	12	0.2	12	
11:12:58																End of Run 2.2 & Start P5	
11:14:03																End of P5 & Start Run 2.3 @ FL047	
11:15:00	60	0.07	9259														

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.1	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.5 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 408

Date: 26/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	MVD	LWC		
11:17:00	35	0.08	9260														
11:19:00	45	0.08	9263														
11:21:00	50	0.08	9381														
11:23:00	50	0.08	9614														
11:24:15																End of Run 2.3	
11:24:55	60	0.08														Start Profile 6 from FL051	
11:26:21	310	0.32	9767			3	100								12	FL040	
11:27:35	125	0.08	9874													FL030	
11:28:33	135	0.08														FL020	
11:29:33	120	0.08														FL010	
11:31:28																End of P6 @ 500'	
11:31:54																Start Run 3.1 @ 500'	
11:32:00	140	0.08	9875														
11:34:00	145	0.08															
11:36:00	145	0.08															
11:38:00	170	0.08															
11:40:00	135	0.08	9876														
11:42:00	130	0.07															
11:42:31																End of Run 3.1 & Start Profile 7	
11:43:24	110	0.07														FL010	
11:44:25	100	0.08														FL020	
11:45:10	100	0.08														FL030	
11:46:18																End of P7& Start Run 3.2 @ FL038	
11:47:00	270	0.3	10112			8	100	230	15				250	18	0.6	12	
11:49:00	410	0.35	10508			10	150	200	13				200	18	0.5	12	
11:51:00	600	0.40	10611			5	200	190	16				210	19	0.6	12	
11:54:00	400	0.40	85			3	150	200	15				200	20	0.6	12	
11:56:00	400	0.40	400			1											
11:56:35																End of Run 3.2& Start Profile 8	
11:57:38																End of P8 & Start Run 3.3 @ FL047	
11:58:00	60	0.08	508														
12:00:00	75	0.08	590														
12:02:00	60	0.08	603														
12:04:00	60	0.08	604														
12:06:00	60	0.08	633														
12:07:40																End of Run 3.3	
12:08:12	45	0.09	645													Start Profile 9 from FL051	
12:09:45	390	0.32	1135			16	150	230	12				200	10	0.1	12	
12:10:42	115	0.27	1328			1										FL030	
12:11:50	140	0.12														FL020	
12:12:45	175	0.08														FL010	
12:14:29	140	0.08	1329													End of Profile 9 @ 50'	
12:15:03																Start Run 4.1 @ 500'	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.1	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.5 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 408

Date: 26/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
12:16:00	115	0.08	1330														
12:18:00	130	0.08	1331														
12:20:00	160	0.08	1332														
12:22:00	170	0.07															
12:24:00	100	0.08															
12:25:28	100	0.08														End of Run 4.1 & Start Profile 10 from 500'	
12:26:35	90	0.8														FL010	
12:27:40	110	0.08														FL020	
12:28:20	100	0.08														FL030	
12:28:12																End of P10 & Start Run 4.2 @ FL040	
12:29:00	500	0.40	1702			18	175	110	18				130	20	0.6	12	
12:31:00	550	0.40	1842			11	150	135	17				150	21	0.7	12	
12:33:00	630	0.40	2298			10	200	180	17				170	20	0.7	1	
12:35:00	300	0.37	2590			10	100	200	14				250	18	0.5	12	
12:39:12																End of Run 4.2 & Start Profile 11	
12:40:09																End of Profile 11 & Start Run 4.4 @ FL040	
12:42:00	40	0.08	0													FFSSP B407B	
11:44:00	40	0.08															
11:46:00	50	0.08															
11:48:00	55	0.08															
11:50:00																End of Run 4.3 & Start Profile 12	
12:40:50	30	0.08	1													FL060	
12:53:01	10	0.09														FL070	
12:54:02	20	0.09														FL080	
12:55:10	20	0.09														FL090	
12:56:19	15	0.09	2													FL100	
12:57:29	10	0.09														FL110	
12:58:25	5	0.08														FL120	
12:59:25	5	0.09														FL130	
13:00:20	3	0.09														FL140	
13:01:06	1	0.09														End of Profile 12 & Start P13 @ FL148	
13:02:23	5	0.09	3													FL140	
13:03:31	8	0.08														FL130	
13:04:32	10	0.08														FL120	
13:05:26	7	0.08														FL110	
13:06:22	13	0.09														FL100	
13:07:23	20	0.09														FL090	
13:08:20	25	0.09														FL080	
13:09:30	15	0.09	4													FL070	
13:10:28	25	0.08														FL060	
13:11:20	45	0.08														FL050	
13:12:15	110	0.21	68			6	75	85	9				110	10	0.1	12	
13:13:37	115	0.08	309													FL030	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.1	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.5 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 408

Date: 26/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
13:14:30	120	0.07	310													FL020	
13:15:37	110	0.08														FL010	
13:18:40	140	0.08														End of Profile @ 50'	
13:19:04																Start Run 5.1 @ 500'	
13:20:00	144	0.08															
13:22:00	120	0.08	315														
13:24:00	130	0.07	317														
13:26:00	115	0.08	319														
13:28:00	115	0.08	323														
13:29:29																End of Run 5.1@ Start Profile P15	
13:30:21	95	0.08	324													FL010	
13:31:19	90	0.08														FL020	
13:32:16	140	0.15	354													FL030	
13:32:57																End of Profile 15 & Start Run 5.2 FL040	
13:33:00	130	0.30	614			4	100	200	12				180	15	0.3	12	
13:35:00	160	0.31	916			10	100	200	13				170	16	0.35	12	
13:37:00	110	0.28	1293			3	100	200	13				190	13	0.4	12	
13:39:00	300	0.39	2225			8	175	200	14				220	19	0.8	12	
13:41:00	700	0.42	3052			21	250	200	14				230	19	0.6	12	
13:44:04																End of Run 5.2 & Start P16	
13:45:07																End of P16 & Start Run 5.3 @ P16 @ FL	
13:46:00	65	0.07	3792														
13:48:00	45	0.08															
13:50:00	20	0.09															
13:52:00	65	0.08	3793														
13:54:00	50	0.08															
13:55:07																End of Run & Start P17	
13:56:17	190	0.28	3899			9	100	100	15				110	10	0.3	12	
13:57:30	130	0.08	3949													FL040	
13:58:09	120	0.08														FL030	
13:59:14	130	0.08														FL020	
14:00:56																FL010	
14:01:15																End of P17 @ 200'	
14:02:00	115	0.08														Start Run 6.1 @ 500'	
14:04:00	130	0.08															
14:06:00	140	0.08															
14:08:00	150	0.08	3950														
14:10:00	150	0.08	3951														
14:11:36																End of Run & Start Profile 18	
14:12:30	150	0.08														FL010	
14:13:25	170	0.08														FL020	
14:14:16	190	0.16	4029													FL030	
14:15:01																End of Profile 18 & Start Run 6.2 @ 3300'	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.1	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.5 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

BA08

Flight:

B408

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B408

Date: 26/oct/08

Instruments

CVI -	ok
Neph –PSAP – wetNeph	ok
SWS -	ok, using manual shutter control
SHIMS -	upper ok but evidence of not being cleaned before flight Lower recovered later in flight
AMS	some data from return leg, instrument requires work
Core Chem -	CO good, using manual calcs SO2 ok Nox ok O3 ozone overheat due to high cabin temperatures before flight
Cloud physics -	evidence of instrument noise generated by other kit on aircraft FSSP – some hard disc crashes – annoyance rather than important
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	ok, possible no data until run 3.1
CCN -	ok except for blue screen of death for 13:17 -> 13:27
VACC -	good operation PAN ok CPC – tests required
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

Printer not responding although connected to network – needs sorting

Mission Scientist 1 Ethernet connection at cabin wall broken by brute strength of MS1. temp fix by connection to old point by spare cable.

Spare laptop required for MS3 position

ISDN Emails

1 email

MPDS

Run for approx 4 hours

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Issues

Aircraft cabin hot preflight

Upper BBRs need cleaning before every flight

P.S.A.P. Log

Flight No. **B408**

Date 26 Oct 08

Page 1 of .. operator

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$	Ph_det levels		Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time: done 082450Z	New filter Tr = 1.000 done	Set to 3.0 lpm: N/A	10.1	18	43	Ave =30 s	←-Preflight
	1.0						
102800	.991		.0	17	46		pump off cloud
103000	.984		14.4	17	46		pump on
105414	.974		.0	17	46		pump off for cloud
111400							pump on
1125							pump off
1128	.972		.0	17	46		pump on
114234	.968		.0	17	46		pump off
115730	.971		.0	17	46		pump on
120830	.978		.0	17	46		pump off
121230	.964		5.2	17	46		pump on
122600	.961		.0	17	46		pump off
123950	.964		.0	17	46		pump on
1330	.953		.0	17	46		pump off
134515	.959		.0	17	46		pump on
1356	.955		140.3	16	46		pump off
135930	.950		4.8	16	46		pump on
141300	.948		.0	16	46		pump off
143730							pump off - filter removed

VOCALS FILTERS

KNB MC B = BOTH

SIZE	#	CHARGED	FLIGHT/DATE	DISCHARGED
10	1	25/10 B	B408 (KNB)	27/10
1	2			
10	3	25/10 S	B408	27/10
1	4			
10	7	25/10 B	B408	27/10
1	8			
10	21	25/10 B	B408	27/10
1	23			
10	33	25/10 B	B408	27/10
1	40			
10	10	25/10 B	B408	27/10
1	69			

#	LOC	Ten	Tolt	Run	Acc Vol	Tot Vol
1, 2, 49	U	101945	102948	R1.2	0, 548	-
3, 4, 140	U	110016	111021	R2.2	578	1125
33, 40, 152	U	115335	120535	R3.2	578	578
7, 8, 117	L	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	0
10, 11, 117	L	100834	101840	R1.1	598	-
21, 23, 83	L	104848	103851	R2.1	602	1146
10, 11, 117	L	114320	115331	R3.1	667	667

CVI log

10/26/08 7:39:18 AM
10/26/08 7:39:28 AM
10/26/08 7:39:33 AM
10/26/08 9:15:30 AM Post take off cfvalve closed cf cntl to 1
10/26/08 9:15:45 AM LA dil at 0.5
10/26/08 9:16:02 AM CPC capped and isolated
10/26/08 9:16:14 AM No SP2 or UHSS
10/26/08 9:17:52 AM clear air, high, aerosol mode
10/26/08 9:18:31 AM AMS knackered for 1st half of flight, only AMS CPC @ 0.6 lpm
10/26/08 9:23:21 AM cf cntl to 1.5 as flow -ve ??ok
10/26/08 9:29:12 AM cf on, entering cloud
10/26/08 9:29:39 AM cf at 5.5
10/26/08 9:30:44 AM out of cloud
10/26/08 9:30:53 AM LA dil back to 0.1
10/26/08 9:31:42 AM cf back to 1.4 and cf valve closed, aerosol mode
10/26/08 9:36:27 AM
10/26/08 9:36:34 AM
10/26/08 9:36:44 AM
10/26/08 9:36:57 AM
10/26/08 9:37:02 AM
10/26/08 9:38:34 AM LA seems noisy or maybe structure?, not much changed when dil
changed from 0.5 to 0.1
10/26/08 9:39:45 AM point A 500ft aerosol mode PCASP approx230
10/26/08 9:43:28 AM PCASP sample adjusted down from 1.2 to approx 1.0
10/26/08 9:44:19 AM LA Dil to 0.5 to see any more structure
10/26/08 9:49:29 AM 3min run just below cloud, set up CF. start at 6 and work down.
set AMS to 0,6lpm
10/26/08 9:49:54 AM 3min run just below cloud, set up CF. start at 6 and work down.
set AMS to 0,6lpm
10/26/08 9:50:28 AM well profile to set up level but started for zero anyway
10/26/08 9:50:51 AM
10/26/08 9:52:22 AM
10/26/08 9:55:00 AM
10/26/08 9:55:11 AM
10/26/08 9:55:58 AM
10/26/08 9:57:11 AM
10/26/08 9:58:10 AM
10/26/08 9:59:26 AM in cloud
10/26/08 10:00:28 AM in cloud proper start of run
10/26/08 10:01:10 AM very high counter flow beneath cloud.
10/26/08 10:01:29 AM cf:8.5
10/26/08 10:01:49 AM cf flow 3.89lpm
10/26/08 10:02:16 AM cf flow 3.89lpm
10/26/08 10:03:54 AM pcasp flow altered bit low
10/26/08 10:04:03 AM adjusted up
10/26/08 10:04:50 AM clear patch
10/26/08 10:05:13 AM climbing for cloud
10/26/08 10:05:44 AM CF set up issues:
10/26/08 10:06:14 AM couldn't get good zero!, fall out flow cloud?
10/26/08 10:06:26 AM back in cloud
10/26/08 10:07:56 AM high levels on PCASP 1300 to 2000 for while
10/26/08 10:08:46 AM
10/26/08 10:13:31 AM check for cf mode zero above cloud before aerosol run
10/26/08 10:13:54 AM cloud top at 4400 run at 4800
10/26/08 10:14:38 AM good zero at cf of 8.5
10/26/08 10:15:08 AM cf to 2 and cf valve shut
10/26/08 10:15:56 AM cf to 1.5 and cf valve shut
10/26/08 10:16:43 AM cf to 1.5 and cf valve shut
10/26/08 10:25:31 AM profile down through cloud cf up and on
10/26/08 10:27:21 AM out of cloud
10/26/08 10:28:20 AM try to set up new zero well below cloud AMS knows.
10/26/08 10:28:27 AM try to set up new zero well below cloud AMS knows.
10/26/08 10:29:08 AM ams flow 0.6 dialed in, looking for new zero
10/26/08 10:32:44 AM ams flow 0.6 dialed in, looking for new zero
10/26/08 10:33:17 AM zero at 2.5 plus 0.3. this normal at 500ft
10/26/08 10:33:26 AM to aerosol mode
10/26/08 10:35:21 AM to aerosol mode

10/26/08 10:39:25 AM LA dill to 1.0
10/26/08 10:40:16 AM LA dill to 1.0 less noise, maybe.
10/26/08 10:42:42 AM
10/26/08 10:43:03 AM cf on at 2.8 during profile up for cloud
10/26/08 10:45:04 AM pretty good zero for 2.8 CFcntl, cf flow:1.62. AMS CPC drawing.
10/26/08 10:45:41 AM in cloud
10/26/08 10:48:05 AM no sig change in LA from out
10/26/08 10:48:14 AM no sig change in LA from out of cloud to in cloud
10/26/08 10:57:25 AM profile up above cloud ct at 4400, leave for zero then goto aerosol mode.
10/26/08 11:01:07 AM PCASP flow tweeked#
10/26/08 11:06:16 AM PCASP flow tweeked again, bit to high
10/26/08 11:08:24 AM CF on at 2.8
10/26/08 11:09:21 AM in cloud
10/26/08 11:10:57 AM out off cloud
10/26/08 11:10:59 AM out off cloud
10/26/08 11:11:42 AM CF off aerosol mode
10/26/08 11:15:08 AM AMS CPC to rosemount
10/26/08 11:15:20 AM AMS CPC to rosemount flow dial to zero
10/26/08 11:26:17 AM CF on at 2.8, AMS CPC on at 0.6
10/26/08 11:28:16 AM in cloud
10/26/08 11:31:58 AM AMS back on fully. Still seeing some organics but not totaly sure what. All clear untill in cloud.
10/26/08 11:33:59 AM Note AMS flow rate at 0.6 instead of 0.72. wont change mid run.
10/26/08 11:38:41 AM LA dill to 0.5, try to see some structure.
10/26/08 11:39:32 AM AMS to rosemount above cloud.
10/26/08 11:40:38 AM CF off aerosol mode.
10/26/08 11:40:56 AM CF off aerosol mode.
10/26/08 11:48:03 AM AMS to stay on rosemount for decending through cloud transitions. Only on CVI for cloud runs proper.
10/26/08 12:11:38 PM cf on ready for cloud transition no ams dial at zero.
10/26/08 12:12:03 PM cloud
10/26/08 12:13:07 PM out of cloud
10/26/08 12:13:23 PM no change seen in LA
10/26/08 12:13:50 PM CF off Aerosol mode.
10/26/08 12:29:45 PM
10/26/08 12:30:17 PM CF on with AMS during profile up ready for cloud
10/26/08 12:32:18 PM in cloud
10/26/08 12:44:37 PM out of cloud cf off
10/26/08 12:48:39 PM AMS only just changed to rosemount
10/26/08 12:49:18 PM LA not showing any change in/out of cloud.
10/26/08 12:56:18 PM clouds
10/26/08 12:56:59 PM clouds, not ready cf just on!
10/26/08 12:57:41 PM out of cloud, cf off.
10/26/08 1:12:30 PM cf on 2.8 ready for cloud run. AMS still on rosemount, dial at zero.
10/26/08 1:13:06 PM AMS on CVI, dial to .72
10/26/08 1:13:14 PM
10/26/08 1:14:37 PM in cloud
10/26/08 1:18:17 PM cloud thinning, decending to 3200
10/26/08 1:21:18 PM cloud patchy
10/26/08 1:27:32 PM AMS still on CVI
10/26/08 1:37:16 PM CF on, staright into cloud,
10/26/08 1:47:20 PM E.O.S.
10/26/08 1:47:48 PM CF to 8 for landing

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 4 08

page 1 of 2

Date: 26/10/2008 Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Pacific Ocean, off the north Chilean coast.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0833	—		EH	C	-51	-30	Cold/Hot cal script.
~0850							System re-start as UI of ARIES software became unresponsive.
~0900	Take off	NOTE:	Time Error	—	ARIES		seems to think UK is in summer time!
0927				C	70.7	36.4	Possible CBB runaway - been steadily increasing since power up.
							Cloud base ~ 2500 ft.
0934	R1						
0934.35	500ft	NZ Long Run		0	70.5	40.6	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec. Below cloud CBB settling at ~40C?
	R2.1						
09.49	End of run						
	R2.2						In cloud?
1000	R2.2 3200ft				71	34	In cloud CBB dipping
1014	R2.3 4800ft	CH 1 min	CH	C	71	30	Cold Hot 1 min script
1015.54		120x1	N	0	71	30	
1017.10		NZ Long	N	0	71	30	
1018	4800ft	Z Long 3 min	Z	0	71	30	Zenith Long Run 3 min script
1024	End of run						
1025.02	↓		CH	C	71	29	Cold Hot 1 min script
1032	R3.1 200ft		CH	C	71	30	— " —
1033.27	"	120x1	Z	0	71	29	
1034	"		N	C	71	30	Nadir Long Run 3 min
1042	P↑		CH	C	71	30	Cold Hot 1 min script
1057	R3.3		CH	C			— " —
1058	4900ft	120x1	N	C	71	28	
1100			Z	0	71	27	Zenith Long Run 3 min script
1107	↓		CH	C	71	28	Cold Hot 1 min script
1113	~200ft		CH	C	71	29	— " —
1115	500ft		NZ	0	70	29	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec.
1125	End of run						
1129	4200ft		CH	C	71	30	Cold Hot 1 min script

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	26/10/08	Flight	B408	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Campaign	VOCALS			
Departure	0900 UTC	Arrival				

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	Done					•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers	Done					•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers	Done					•
FERA on				at time	0825	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	54°C	Ch	58°C	Ch18	40.1°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on				at time	0832	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	291.3	Cold	290.5		
Target heating	20.0					•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	0837	
Scan indication		Monitor	•		Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software				at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor			Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	
Brightness temps 'sensible'				•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold	
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B
	(39.9)	(32.1)	(45.0)	(40.9)
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)
				Ch20
				(44-48)

Power changeover

Headset on before start		•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		•
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	•
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Flight #	B408	Date	26/10/08	Operator(s)	JNB	log page	2	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
0842			Good start up – no problems to note						
1007			Horace connection fell out just as belts went on and have been unable to locate it! Will look harder during transit						
1011			Horace located and restored. Yey me!						
1016			Transit above 8/8 SC5 @ 3700ft below 1/8 AS2						
102242	P2	FL010	Start of profile 2 descent from FL010 to 50 ft						
102906	P2	FL037	Into SC5 layer						
103034	P2	FL027	Below SC5 layer at approx FL027						
103309	P2	50ft	End of profile descent at 50ft						
103359	1	FL005	Start of run						
103915	2.1	FL005	Under 8/8 SC5 for entire of run 1 and run 2.1						
104946	2.1	FL005	End of run						
104946	P4		Start of profile to FL021 just below cloud base						
105103	??	FL021	Start of run just below 8/8 SC5						
			End of run						
105930	P4		Into cloud						
110019	2.2	FL031	End of profile climb						
110541	2.2	FL036	Climbed to FL036 to keep up with cloud base						
111257	P5		End of run start of profile 5						
111257	P5		End of profile 5						
111404	2.3	FL047	Start of run 2.3 above cloud 8/8 SC5 below clear skies						
112434	2.3	FL047	End of run followed by non profile climb to FL053						
112457	P6	FL053	Profile descent from FL053						
112605	P6		Entered sc5						
112715	P6	FL035	Below cloud 8/8 sc5 at FL032						
113138	P6	FL002	End of profile						
113150	3.1	FL005	Start of run below 8/8 SC5 though beginning to thin in places						
1138	!	!	Can't see any data logs so have closed log and restarted again – will continue to monitor						
114229	3.1	FL005	End of run						
114229	P7	FL005	Start of climb to FL040 SC5 now 7/8						
1145	P7		Entering cloud						
??	P7	FL039	End of profile						
114622	3.2	FL039	Start of run 3.2 in cloud (7.9 Oktas)						
1156	3.2	FL039	End of run						
113651	P8		Start of profile out of cloud at FL044						
115738	3.3	FL049	End of profile start of run above 7/8 SC5 (7.0 Oktas)						
120801	3.3	FL049	End of run and quick pop up to start profile						
120813	P9	FL053	Start of profile descent						
120930	P9		Entered 7/8 SC5 (Still a good 7.9 Oktas)						
121050	P9		Below 7/8 SC5						
121352	P9		Point B						
1214	P9	FL002	End of profile and pop up to FL005						
121503	4.1	FL005	Start of run below 8/8 SC5						
	4.1	FL005	End of run						

Flight #	B408	Date	26/10/08	Operator(s)	JNB	log page	3	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
122528	P10	FL005	Start of profile						
122800	P10	FL036	Into SC5 which is deffo 8/8 at this end (west)						
122909	P10	FL042	End of profile to FL042						
122909	4.2	FL042	Start of run 4.2 in 8/8 SC5						
1232	!	!	Seen first data log so hopefully prob resolved though not sure how much data was lost from first part of flight						
123921	4.2	FL042	End of run						
123921	P11	FL042	Start of profile climb						
124012	P11	FL049	End of profile climb						
124012	4.3	FL049	Start of run above 8/8 SC5 below clear skies						
125041	4.3	FL049	End of run						
125041	P12	FL049	Start of profile climb to FL150						
130112	P12/13	FL150	End of profile climb and into descent to 50ft						
1305	P13		Cloud deffo 7/8 sc5 at this east end of the runs still nil above						
1313	P13		Into Sc5 layer						
1314	P13		And below 7/8 SC5 again						
1315	!	!	Second data file seen so looking good I think						
131841	P13/14	50ft	End of profile descent at 50 ft then climb to FL005 for run (Profiles ascent 14).						
131903	5.1	FL005	Start of run below 7/8 SC5 (7.5 Oktas)						
132933	5.1	FL005	End of run and start of profile climb						
132933	P15	FL005	Start of profile climb to FL040						
133258	5.2	FL040	Start of in cloud run appear to be in top part of 7.5 Oktas SC5						
134407	5.2	FL040	End of run start of profile climb						
134445	P16	FL042 ?	Out of 7/8 SC5 and above it, below clear skies						
134523	5.3	FL049	Start of above cloud run						
135509	5.3	FL049	End of run						
135509	P17	FL049	Start of profile descent to FL002						
135635	P17		Into 7/8 SC5						
135845	P17		Below 7/8 SC5						
140118	P17	FL002	End of profile descent followed by climb to FL005						
140118	6.1	FL005	Start of run 6.1 below 7/8 SC5						
1405	!	!	Further data file noted – confident all is now working well.						
	6.1	FL005	End of run						
141136	P18	FL005	Start of profile ascent to FL038						
		FL030	Into 7/8 SC5 but popped out of top whilst heading for FL038. Run will be conducted at FL033						
141501	6.2	FL033	Start of run in thin 7/8 SC5						
141800	6.2	FL032	Descent to FL032 as SC5 increasingly thin as we head towards the East end of the run (towards coast)						
142115	6.2	FL031	Back above cloud so descending to FL031 still 7/8 but increasingly thin and becoming patchy						
142531	6.2	FL031	End of run start of profile ascent to FL039						

Flight #	B408	Date	26/10/08	Operator(s)	JNB	log page	4	of	4
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>				Sys		

142531	P19	FL031	Start of profile ascent to FL039 500ft above cloud still 7/8 SC5 but very thin and below 1/8 Ci (Con/Chemtrails)	
142616	6.3	FL039	Start of run above 7/8 thin SC5 and below 1/8 Ci1	
143648	P20	FL039	End of run	
143726	P20	FL039	Start of profile descent	
143726	6.4	FL034	Start of run (barely) in cloud SC5 more like cloud tops then in the actual layer	
143726	6.4	FL034	End of run	
			End of science	

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B..408**

Date .26/10/08.

Operator's name D Tiddeman.....

Page .1..... of

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
10:20:30		10k						humidifier on
10:22						20		
10:34:20	R2	500ft	13.7	45.8	47.1	40	20	
10:40:28	R2.1	500ft	13.7	42.9	76.1	45	40	
10:44:57	R2.1	500ft	13.9	44.5	82.9	5	45	
10:55:00	R2	2100ft	13.1	42.2	45.3	-	13	humidifier off for cloud ru
11:14:54		4600ft	12.0	4.7	36.	5	19	humidifier back on
11:19:00	R2.3	4800ft	12.1	4.1	26.0	45	12	
11:24:30	"	"	11.8	1.5	70.5	5	38	
11:33:13	R3.1	500ft	13.9	42.2	45.9	45	19	
11:40:20	R3.1	500ft	14.0	48.4	87.0	5	44	
11:45								humid off in cloud run
11:56:39	R3.3	4900	7.3	41.1		5	22	humid back on
12:00:35	"	"	12.1	5.0	33.7	45	17	
12:07:30	R3.3		12.1	2.1	75.5	5	43	
12:14:10	R4.1	500	14.0	42.	56	45	17	
12:19:20	R4.1	500	13.9	38	86	5	42	
1228			12.6	38	50	-	16	humid off
12:41:00	R4.3		12.1	6.3	35.7	45	22	humid on
12:47:23	R4.3		12.2	4.1	74.6	5	43	

B408_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

08:15:25.71 --- - - - -
08:15:25.71 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:15:25.71 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:15:25.71 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B408
08:15:25.71 --- - - - -
08:16:59.69 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:17:04.15 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:17:04.71 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:17:50.75 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:17:50.83 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:17:50.92 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:18:10.48 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:18:14.36 SWS - - 100 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:18:16.64 SWS - - - 100 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:18:19.03 SWS - - - 200 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
08:18:19.03 SWS - - - 200 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
08:18:22.49 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:18:24.16 USH - - - 5 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:18:30.27 USH - - - 200 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:18:30.28 USH - - - 200 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:18:33.04 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:18:34.48 LSH - - - 5 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:18:38.33 LSH - - - 200 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:18:38.34 LSH - - - 200 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:18:48.34 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:48.34 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:48.35 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:52.48 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:19:02.26 LSH - - - - Idling
08:19:02.26 SWS - - - - Idling
08:19:02.29 USH - - - - Idling
08:36:55.46 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:36:55.47 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:36:55.47 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:37:04.11 SWS - - - - Idling
08:37:04.19 LSH - - - - Idling
08:37:04.19 USH - - - - Idling
08:37:40.15 --- - - - - *** 16 deg C
08:39:17.37 --- - - - - *** 15 deg C
08:42:57.16 --- - - - - *** 14 deg
08:46:07.50 --- - - - - *** 13 deg
08:49:32.32 --- - - - - *** 12 deg C
08:51:25.63 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
08:51:27.30 SWS 171.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:51:38.58 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:51:55.99 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:52:11.46 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:52:21.50 SWS - - - - Idling
08:52:23.47 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:23.47 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:23.48 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:25.82 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:52:27.17 SWS - - - - Idling
08:52:27.20 LSH - - - - Idling
08:52:27.23 USH - - - - Idling
08:52:33.99 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:33.99 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:34.00 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:34.42 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:53:01.49 SWS - - - - Idling
08:53:01.65 LSH - - - - Idling
08:53:01.65 USH - - - - Idling
08:53:05.57 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:53:35.69 SWS - - - - Idling
08:54:21.41 --- - - - - *** 13 deg C
09:33:50.20 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

09:33:50.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:50.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:35:32.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg C
09:36:08.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
09:36:31.67	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 110.000
09:36:32.79	SWS	110.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:41:10.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:41:10.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:41:10.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:41:17.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
09:42:53.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:53.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:53.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:03.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:05.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:09.40	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:43:17.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:19.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:20.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:22.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:25.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:27.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:30.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:33.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:48.27	SWS	110.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:08:49.41	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:09:07.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:09:12.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:15.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:09:17.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:19.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:09:57.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
10:10:16.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:19.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:23.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:23.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:23.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:10:25.08	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:10:28.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:05.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:05.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:11:08.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:11:30.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:31.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:11:33.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:03.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:06.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:07.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:10.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:26.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:35.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:13.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1
10:13:14.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:14.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:14.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:21.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:15:32.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:32.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:32.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:37.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:38.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:38.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:15:39.68	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:15:41.37	SWS	172.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:15:43.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:43.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:43.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:00.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:03.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:19:00.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:02.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:10.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:19:13.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:13.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:13.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:14.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:45.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:15.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:15.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:18.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:55.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:57.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:59.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:00.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:03.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:04.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:04.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:06.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:36.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:02.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 2
10:23:10.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** descent to 50 ft
10:23:14.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:28:43.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:28:53.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
10:29:06.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud now
10:29:12.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
10:29:37.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:37.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:29:38.81	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:29:39.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:40.54	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:30:07.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
10:30:09.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:09.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:11.49	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:30:13.22	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:30:14.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:14.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:14.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:21.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:21.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:21.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:30:24.20	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:30:25.92	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:30:26.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:26.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:26.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:44.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:47.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:16.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:16.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:16.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:16.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:17.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:52.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:54.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:56.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:58.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:18.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:21.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:23.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:34.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:34:05.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at n
10:34:15.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
10:35:00.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:02.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:29.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:39:07.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:39:09.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:19.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at point A
10:39:31.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:39:31.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:39:33.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:45.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:47.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:39:49.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:52.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:39:53.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:56.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:08.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:11.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:13.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:18.34	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
10:40:18.34	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
10:40:20.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:21.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:23.96	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
10:40:23.96	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
10:40:26.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:26.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:28.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:49.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:50.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:52.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:53.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:41:05.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:07.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:08.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:39.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:40.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:42.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:24.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:49:28.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:29.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:32.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:32.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:32.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:33.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:50.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:51.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:53.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:54.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:50:09.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:11.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:50:12.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:03.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 min run below cloud
10:53:35.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:36.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:46.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:53:58.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:53:58.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:00.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:20.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:21.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:24.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:24.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:27.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:28.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:42.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:44.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:45.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:01.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud run at 3200 ft
11:00:04.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:00:09.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:10.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:16.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 2.2
11:01:04.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12\ deg

11:02:26.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:26.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:02:28.71	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:02:30.45	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:02:31.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:31.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:31.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:50.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:04:11.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:11.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:11.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:14.48	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:04:16.20	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:04:16.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:16.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:16.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:32.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:32.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:32.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:34.74	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:06:36.46	SWS	172.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:06:37.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:37.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:37.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:06.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:06.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:06.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:08.72	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:08:10.46	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:08:12.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:12.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:12.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:30.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:30.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:30.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:33.06	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:10:34.79	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:10:36.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:36.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:36.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:43.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:44.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:46.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:46.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:46.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:48.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:54.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:08.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:12:08.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:12:10.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:18.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:19.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:12:20.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:21.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:12:22.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:23.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:12:32.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:35.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:36.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:47.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:16:48.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:28.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:22:00.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:01.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:27.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:53.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:55.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:23:04.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:05.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

11:23:05.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:23:13.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:23:13.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:23:13.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:23:15.89	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:23:19.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:19.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:19.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:19.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:23:20.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:23:20.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:23:22.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:23:24.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:23:24.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:23:24.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:03.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:04.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:04.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:07.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:53.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:53.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:53.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:55.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:56.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:10.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:11.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:12.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:13.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:15.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:16.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:24.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:37.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:37.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:37.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:39.39	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:27:41.12	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:27:41.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:41.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:41.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:26.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:28.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:29.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:30.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:13.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3.1 at 500 ft
11:32:16.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:34:18.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:19.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:20.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:22.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:35.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:36.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:37.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:39.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:39.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:39.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:39.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:41.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:52.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:53.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:54.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:55.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:56.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:56.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:57.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:57.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:58.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:59.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:13.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:16.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:38:05.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:42:37.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:38.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:40.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:42.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:42:42.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:42:43.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:45.20	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:42:48.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:50.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:42:51.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:26.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:27.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:29.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:29.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:44.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:32.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:47:09.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:09.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:09.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:12.01	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:47:13.73	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:47:20.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:20.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:20.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:08.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:09.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:10.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:12.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:12.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:13.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:16.89	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:50:18.62	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:50:20.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:20.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:48.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:48.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:48.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:49.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:50.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:51:29.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:51:30.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:51:31.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:51:32.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:51:44.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:02.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:54:54.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:55:22.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:22.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:22.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:22.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:55:24.52	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:55:25.73	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:55:26.29	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:55:30.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:30.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:30.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:20.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:21.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:22.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:24.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:46.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:46.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:46.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:48.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:51.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:01.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:02.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:04.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:57:05.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:18.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:57.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:05:53.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:54.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:55.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:57.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:50.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:51.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:53.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:56.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:56.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:56.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:57.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:58.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:06.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:07.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:07.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:10.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:11.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:12.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:13.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:21.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:21.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:35.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:13:23.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:23.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:23.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:23.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:24.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:26.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:36.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:37.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:38.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:39.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:52.19	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:13:55.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:10.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:10.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:10.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:11.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:11.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:14:11.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:12.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:13.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:14:29.82	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:14:31.57	SWS	-5.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:15:13.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:10.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:11.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:12.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:14.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:14.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:15.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:15.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:17.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:27.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:28.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:30.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:31.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:32.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:33.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:34.51	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:27:43.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:43.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:55.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:35:26.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:27.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:27.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:35:30.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:19.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:19.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:19.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:20.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:22.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:30.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:31.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:33.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:34.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:42.46	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:36:44.25	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:36:49.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:52.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:53.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:54.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:57.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:41:28.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:41:29.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:41:30.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:41:32.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:41:53.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:42:13.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:13.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:13.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:16.21	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:42:17.98	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:42:19.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:42:19.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:42:19.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:42:57.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:57.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:57.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:02.21	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:43:03.92	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:43:06.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:06.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:06.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:48:15.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
12:50:41.65	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:50:43.39	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:51:22.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:22.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:22.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:25.80	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:51:27.59	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:51:30.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:30.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:30.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:34.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:35.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:36.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:38.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:46.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:46.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:46.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:47.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:48.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:10.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:11.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:52:13.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:14.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:52:16.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:16.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:52:20.01	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:52:29.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:31.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:32.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:33.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:52:35.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:52:44.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:56:33.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:56:33.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:56:33.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:56:35.42	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:56:37.19	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:56:38.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:56:38.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:56:38.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:56:43.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:56:44.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:56:45.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:56:47.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:08.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:08.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:08.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:09.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:11.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:18.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:19.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:20.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:21.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:23.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:24.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:33.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:39.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:03:59.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:03:59.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:03:59.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:02.58	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:04:04.33	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:04:06.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:06.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:06.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:17.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:08:12.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:13.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:14.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:17.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:22.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:22.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:22.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:23.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:26.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:35.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:36.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:38.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:39.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:41.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:42.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:49.13	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:08:50.94	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:08:51.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:57.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:58.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:01.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:03.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:22.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:22.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:22.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:24.16	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:09:25.93	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:09:27.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:27.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:27.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:52.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:52.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:52.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:09:55.03	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:09:56.82	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:09:59.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:59.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:59.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:30.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloud
13:13:12.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
13:24:26.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12\deg
13:29:31.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:31.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:31.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:33.40	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:29:56.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:57.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:58.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:59.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:00.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:01.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:13.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:13.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:13.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:15.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:16.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:16.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:19.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:09.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:32:24.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** entering cloud
13:32:58.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** in clod run at 4000 ft
13:33:21.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:33:31.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:33:36.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:36.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:36.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:47.36	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
13:33:47.37	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
13:33:50.82	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
13:33:50.83	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
13:33:59.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:00.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:03.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:04.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:04.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:05.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:06.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:06.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:07.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:08.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:24.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:24.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:24.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:27.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:28.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:29.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:31.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:51.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:52.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:52.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:52.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:34:52.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:53.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:54.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:37.76	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
13:35:37.77	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
13:35:39.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:39.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:40.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:41.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:44.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:46.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

13:35:56.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:56.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:56.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:58.88	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:36:00.69	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:36:02.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:02.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:02.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:05.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:06.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:07.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:10.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:07.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:08.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:09.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:11.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:11.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:12.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:13.27	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:41:15.06	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:41:27.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:28.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:29.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:30.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:31.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:32.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:33.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:34.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:51.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:51.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:54.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:54.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:55.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:57.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:12.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
13:45:10.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:10.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:10.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:12.63	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:45:14.39	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:45:18.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:29.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:31.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:33.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:34.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:34.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:35.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:42.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:42.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:11.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:11.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:12.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:15.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:43.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:43.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:43.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:44.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:46.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:54.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:55.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:56.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:57.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:58.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:58.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:55:09.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:26.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:57:04.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:05.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:05.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:57:08.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:13.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:13.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:13.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:18.02	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:01:19.83	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:01:29.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:29.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:29.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:33.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:33.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:34.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:37.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:58.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:59.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:02.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:04.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:07.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:07.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:10.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:11.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:12.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:12.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:39.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:11:39.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:11:39.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:11:49.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:50.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:11:51.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:52.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:11:53.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:54.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:12:07.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:07.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:07.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:09.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:09.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:12.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:12:14.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:02.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3330 ft in cloud
14:17:14.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:18:05.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:18:05.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:18:05.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:18:05.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:18:06.81	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:18:08.58	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:18:10.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:18:10.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:18:10.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:16.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:16.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:16.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:19.06	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:20:20.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:20:23.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:23.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:23.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:06.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:06.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:06.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:06.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:08.50	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:23:10.29	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:23:11.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:11.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:11.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:25:57.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:58.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:26:01.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:03.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:15.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:16.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:17.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:17.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:18.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:19.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:28.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:29.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:29.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:32.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:47.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:36:45.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:36:45.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:36:45.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:36:47.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:48.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:57.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:58.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:36:59.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:00.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:01.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:02.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:04.23	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:37:11.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:13.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:14.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:14.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:17.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:00.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:02.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:09.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
14:40:54.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:40:54.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:40:54.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:40:56.47	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:40:58.29	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:40:59.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:40:59.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:40:59.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:03.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:41:15.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:41:20.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:20.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:20.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:22.67	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:41:24.45	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:41:25.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:25.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:25.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:27.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:28.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:30.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:32.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:55.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
14:48:27.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:28.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:29.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:31.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:34.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:34.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:34.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:45.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:46.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:47.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:48.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:49.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:50.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:49:00.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:00.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:00.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:02.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:03.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:04.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:06.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:19.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:20.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:21.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:24.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:26.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:26.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:27.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:33.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:34.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:36.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:37.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:38.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:38.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:47.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:47.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:47.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:50.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:50.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:52.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:54.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 26/10/9

Flight No: B 408

Pre-Flighter: Eric Hon

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	MC Toolkit Hanger	Collect spanners for core chem	✓
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☐	CNC	Butanol filled	Left to operator
26	☐	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	☐	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	"
28	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
External Checks				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	Own camera
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	Photographed e/s
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	} ** Check no butanol** to be done by core chem operator (K.T.)
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
Avalon Checks				
44	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B408:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Feb 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

No Digital video avi recordings exist for this flight.

No Digital8 video recordings exist for this flight.